

Is there a relationship between COVID-19 vaccination coverage and economic recovery across countries?

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Release date: 17/10/2025

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19489627>

Our analysis reveals no significant relationship between COVID-19 vaccination coverage and economic recovery across 182 countries. For health recovery, we observe a paradoxical negative association (higher vaccination → worse recovery), which suggests potential reverse causality. For example, countries experiencing worse health outcomes could have intensified their vaccination efforts in response. Unlike Question 1 where inequality's effect was Africa-specific, the vaccination-recovery relationship is universal across regions, suggesting different underlying mechanisms. One should remain prudent in interpreting these results.

Part A: Economic Recovery (GDP)

We found no statistically significant association between vaccination and economic recovery at global level. See Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Global (Including Africa) - Recovery GDP

Variable	β	SE	95% CI	p-value
Vaccination (per 10pp)	+0.0203	0.0131	[-0.0056, 0.0462]	0.123
Vax Speed (per 1000)	+0.0011	0.0176	[-0.0336, 0.0358]	0.949
ln(Health Expenditure)	-0.0520	0.0146	[-0.0808, -0.0231]	< .001
Aging Population	-0.0112	0.0274	[-0.0653, 0.0428]	0.683
Fiscal Balance	+0.0049	0.0030	[-0.0010, 0.0108]	0.102
COVID Severity 2020	+0.0001	0.0002	[-0.0003, 0.0006]	0.649

N = 182, R² = 0.2931, F(12, 169) = 6.28, p < .001

We found no statistically significant association between vaccination and economic recovery in the African region. See Table 2.2.

Table 2.2: Africa Only - Recovery GDP

Variable	β	SE	95% CI	p
Vaccination (per 10pp)	+0.0600	0.0488	[-0.0389, 0.1589]	0.227
Vax Speed (per 1000)	-0.0363	0.0913	[-0.2212, 0.1486]	0.693
ln(Health Expenditure)	-0.0923	0.0187	[-0.1303, -0.0544]	< .001
Aging Population	-0.0554	0.1054	[-0.2688, 0.1580]	0.602
Fiscal Balance	+0.0087	0.0063	[-0.0040, 0.0214]	0.174
COVID Severity 2020	-0.0007	0.0009	[-0.0025, 0.0011]	0.441

N = 45, $R^2 = 0.2726$, $F(6, 38) = 4.70$, $p < .001$

We found no statistically significant association between vaccination and economic recovery in the African region. See Table 2.3

Table 2.3: Non-Africa - Recovery GDP

Variable	β	SE	95% CI	p
Vaccination (per 10pp)	+0.0130	0.0129	[-0.0125, 0.0385]	0.315
Vax Speed (per 1000)	+0.0063	0.0166	[-0.0264, 0.0391]	0.703
ln(Health Expenditure)	-0.0402	0.0172	[-0.0743, -0.0061]	0.021
Aging Population	-0.0102	0.0293	[-0.0681, 0.0477]	0.729
Fiscal Balance	+0.0039	0.0034	[-0.0028, 0.0106]	0.255
COVID Severity 2020	+0.0002	0.0002	[-0.0003, 0.0006]	0.506

N = 137, $R^2 = 0.3058$, $F(10, 126) = 5.75$, $p < .001$

Part B: Health Recovery (change in COVID-19 excess deaths)

Health recovery is proxied by the number of COVID-19 excess death (lower excess deaths = better health recovery). We found that a 10 pp increase in vaccination is associated with a 9.75 reduction in excess death at the global level. We also found that an increase in vaccine speed was associated with a 15.9 % increase in excess deaths, which seems paradoxical. See Table 2.4.

Table 2.4: Global (Including Africa) - Recovery Health

Variable	β	SE	95% CI	p
Vaccination (per 10pp)	-9.75	3.86	[-17.36, -2.14]	0.012
Vax Speed (per 1000)	+15.90	6.22	[3.62, 28.18]	0.011
ln(Health Expenditure)	+0.91	3.57	[-6.14, 7.96]	0.798
Aging Population	-31.75	7.53	[-46.61, -16.90]	< .001
Fiscal Balance	-0.65	0.57	[-1.77, 0.47]	0.252
COVID Severity 2020	-0.10	0.07	[-0.23, 0.04]	0.174

N = 184, $R^2 = 0.3399$, $F(12, 171) = 7.73$, $p < .001$

A 10-percentage-point increase in vaccination coverage is associated with a statistically significant 8.9 % reduction in excess death, indicating **better health recovery**. The positive

association between rollout **speed** and excess deaths likely reflects **reverse causality** (countries with worse mortality accelerated vaccination). See Table 2.5.

Table 2.5: Africa Only - Recovery Health

Variable	β	SE	95% CI	p
Vaccination (per 10pp)	-8.90	4.33	[-17.39, -0.40]	0.047
Vax Speed (per 1000)	+12.24	7.35	[-2.63, 27.11]	0.104
ln(Health Expenditure)	+5.55	2.69	[0.11, 10.99]	0.046
Aging Population	-14.42	12.48	[-39.68, 10.85]	0.255
Fiscal Balance	+1.44	0.67	[0.09, 2.79]	0.037
COVID Severity 2020	-0.20	0.09	[-0.38, -0.03]	0.026

N = 45, $R^2 = 0.3398$, $F(6, 38) = 4.28$, $p < .001$

We found that a 10 pp increase in vaccination is associated with a 10.4 reduction in excess death, slightly larger than in Africa. See Table 2.6

Table 2.6: Non-Africa - Recovery Health

Variable	β	SE	95% CI	p
Vaccination (per 10pp)	-10.44	4.34	[-19.02, -1.86]	0.018
Vax Speed (per 1000)	+16.90	6.93	[3.18, 30.62]	0.016
ln(Health Expenditure)	-0.23	4.54	[-9.22, 8.76]	0.960
Aging Population	-32.26	7.96	[-48.00, -16.52]	< .001
Fiscal Balance	-0.78	0.66	[-2.09, 0.53]	0.240
COVID Severity 2020	-0.09	0.07	[-0.24, 0.05]	0.205

N = 139, $R^2 = 0.3077$, $F(10, 128) = 6.46$, $p < .001$

We found no statistically significant association between COVID-19 vaccination and economic recovery, but a universal correlation between vaccination and health recovery. See Table 2.7

Table 2.7: Regional Comparison of Vaccination Effects

Region	Outcome	β (Vax)	SE	95% CI	p
Global	GDP Recovery	+0.020	0.013	[-0.006, +0.046]	0.123
Africa	GDP Recovery	+0.060	0.049	[-0.039, +0.159]	0.227
Non-Africa	GDP Recovery	+0.013	0.013	[-0.013, +0.038]	0.315
Global	Health Recovery	-9.75	3.86	[-17.36, -2.14]	0.012
Africa	Health Recovery	-8.90	4.33	[-17.39, -0.40]	0.047
Non-Africa	Health Recovery	-10.44	4.34	[-19.02, -1.86]	0.018

Note. All models use robust standard errors and control for health expenditure, ageing population, fiscal balance, COVID-19 severity in 2020, and regional fixed effects (except Africa-only models).

Discussion:

The most striking effect here is the positive positive effect of vaccination in reducing the number of excess deaths and thus support and health recovery.

The absence of a statistically significant association between COVID-19 vaccination and economic recovery was unexpected. This might be the result of mediating and confounding factors that the study could not examine. Among the possible ones, we could mention:

- Different time horizon between vaccination and economic recovery, particularly following unprecedented lockdown measures
- Possible heterogeneity between the North, with high vaccination rates and service-dependent economic structures vulnerable to strict lockdowns, might have a different economic recovery than countries from the South with lower vaccination rates and an economic structure based on export.
- Unequal fiscal policies (stimulus packages, debt) between regions
- The post-COVID period coincided with the Ukraine war and the oil shock

This study has limitations. The cross-sectional design does not enable us to study causality.

Conclusion:

We found no association between vaccination and economic recovery.

As expected, we found that the vaccine is associated with a reduction in excess deaths, supporting health recovery.